

3/20/2021, Aged-SCI lesion volume, cresyl violet staining by Hui, Stereology by Yun

Group	Animal Number	LV (μm^3)	LV (mm^3)
Vehicle	AV11	2555200000	2.56
	AV12	1252800000	1.25
	AV13	3840000000	3.84
	AV14	1992000000	1.99
	AV15	3144000000	3.14
	AV16	1987200000	1.99
	AV17	2731200000	2.73
	AV18	2937600000	2.94
		Mean	2.56
		SEM	0.284
PLX5622	AP11	614400000	0.61
	AP12	1224000000	1.22
	AP13	2288000000	2.29
	AP14	907200000	0.91
	AP15	475200000	0.48
	AP16	2148800000	2.15
	AP17	2355200000	2.36
	AP18	2379200000	2.38
		Mean	1.65
		SEM	0.401

40 um section Junyun did TBI, Hui did sectioning, staining
3w PLX 4w rest 2w TBI, Yun did PLX, body weight, LV analysis by stereology
CCI: 4.3m/s, 1.2mm in 18-mon-old male mice

	Vehicle	PLX
Mean	2.56	1.65
SEM	0.28	0.40
N	8 mice	8 mice

